

SPEAKING THE TRUTH IN LOVE: CHRISTIAN INTEGRITY IN THE AGE OF MISINFORMATION

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Abstract

In an era dominated by digital media, the rapid spread of misinformation, half-truths, and online hostility challenges Christians to uphold biblical principles of truth and love. This paper explores the intersection of faith, integrity, and social engagement in the digital age, drawing from Ephesians 4:15: “Rather, speaking the truth in love, we are to grow up in every way into him who is the head, into Christ” (ESV). As misinformation becomes increasingly prevalent, Christians are called to engage in truthful and loving communication. This paper argues that biblical principles provide a framework for ethical speech, discernment, and social engagement, equipping believers to navigate digital interactions with integrity and grace. A multidisciplinary approach is employed, integrating biblical exegesis, theological reflection, and practical application. Scriptural analysis examines biblical teachings on truth (John 8:32), wisdom (Colossians 4:6), and discernment (1 John 4:1). Contemporary case studies highlight the real-world impact of misinformation on Christian witness. At the same time, interactive discussions provide practical strategies for responsible engagement in digital spaces. By fostering Christ-centered integrity, this paper aims to equip believers to be salt and light (Matthew 5:13-16), offering a redemptive voice in an age of confusion. It further explores the theological, ethical, and pastoral implications of speaking the truth in love in the contemporary age of misinformation.

Keywords: Christian integrity. Age of misinformation. Ethical living. Love. Truth.

INTRODUCTION

Scriptural and Theological Foundations of Truth-Telling

The concept of “Speaking the Truth in Love” is deeply rooted in biblical and theological foundations, emphasizing integrity amidst the challenges of misinformation. The biblical command to speak truth is inseparable from God’s own self-revelation. This principle is derived from the teachings of Jesus and the apostolic writings, which advocate for a commitment to truth tempered by love and compassion. Scripture repeatedly identifies God as the source of

truth, and Christ as its embodiment: “I am the way, and the truth, and the life” (John 14:6). Truth-telling is not simply a moral convention but a participation in the divine nature.

Truth, knowledge, and wisdom are not merely philosophical musings within the Judeo-Christian tradition. Instead, they are deeply rooted in divine revelation and serve as a foundation for understanding reality. The Decalogue’s prohibition, “You shall not bear false witness against your neighbor” (Exod. 20:16), frames falsehood as an offense against both the human community and the God of truth. The following sections provide a detailed exploration of these foundations.

Old Testament on Truth and Wisdom

From Genesis to Malachi, the Hebrew Scriptures consistently highlight the concepts of truth (’emet, אֱמֶת) and wisdom (ḥokmâ, חִכְמָה) as essential divine attributes and principles for leading a righteous life. These terms appear in various contexts, underscoring their deep theological and ethical importance. In the Old Testament, truth is frequently linked to God's character and His faithfulness to the covenant.

For instance, the concept of Truth (’emet, אֱמֶת) is highlighted in Exodus 34:6: “The Lord, the Lord God, merciful and gracious, longsuffering, and abundant in goodness and truth (’emet).” In this verse, truth is presented as a fundamental aspect of God's character, emphasizing that divine truth is inseparable from His mercy and justice. Similarly, in Psalm 25:5, we read, “Lead me in your truth (’emet) and teach me, for you are the God of my salvation.” Here, truth is not merely about propositional accuracy; it represents a path of life—a means through which God guides His people toward salvation. Additionally, Zechariah 8:16 states: “These are the things you shall do: Speak each man the truth (’emet) to his neighbor; give judgment in your gates for truth, justice, and peace.” In this context, truth is closely tied to justice and peace, underscoring its communal and ethical dimensions in fostering a righteous society.

Augustine argued in *De Mendacio* that “every lie is a sin,” for it not only corrupts the speaker but also fractures the bonds of trust that sustain community.ⁱ His concern was that lying distorts. Overall, truth is an abstract concept that is deeply intertwined with divine guidance and salvation. The Hebrew term for truth, “emet,” signifies stability and reliability, suggesting that truth is foundational for building trustworthy relationships with God and others. God’s truth and the image of God in humanity. Similarly, Thomas Aquinas in the *Summa Theologiae* considered lying intrinsically disordered because it “is to speak against one’s own mind with the intention of deceiving,” thereby opposing the virtue of truth that flows from God himself.ⁱⁱ Nicholas Wolterstorff adds that truthfulness belongs to the obligations of covenantal life: God’s people are called to live with integrity in their speech because covenantal relationships depend upon trust.ⁱⁱⁱ

New Testament on Truth and Wisdom

In the New Testament, the Greek word ἀλήθεια (alétheia, “truth”) is central to understanding Jesus’ teachings, the apostles’ writings, and the nature of divine revelation. Truth is revealed as a transformative power in Christian life, emphasizing intellectual and spiritual enlightenment (John 8:31-32). Jesus identifies Himself as the embodiment of ultimate truth, signifying that truth is not merely an abstract concept but a person, Christ Himself. He declares, “I am the way, the truth (alétheia), and the life. No one comes to the Father except through Me.” This assertion not only emphasizes the centrality of truth in the life of believers but also frames truth as relational, rooted in the person of Christ.

While speaking to a group of Jews who believed in Him, Jesus emphasizes that true freedom comes from abiding by His word and knowing the truth, which is ultimately found in Him. This freedom is not just political or social; it is spiritual, liberating people from sin, deception, and ignorance. Jesus states, “Then you will know the truth, and the truth will set you free” (John

8:32). He clarifies that “Everyone who sins is a slave to sin” (John 8:34). The truth He refers to is not merely intellectual knowledge but a transformative reality that frees people from the power of sin. Truth is connected to sanctification, highlighting the purifying and transformative role of God's word in the lives of believers (John 17:17).

The Apostle Paul's understanding of “truth” is never abstract; rather, it is deeply connected to God's redemptive revelation and ethical standards. In Romans 1:18–25, he contrasts truth with idolatry, reflecting the prophetic criticisms of Israel's idol worship found in texts like Isaiah 44:9–20 and Jeremiah 2:11. In this passage, humanity is described as having “exchanged the glory of the immortal God for images” (Rom 1:23). This idea of “exchange” resonates with Psalm 106:20, which mourns Israel's abandonment of God's truth for a “metal image,” positioning truth as a matter of covenant faithfulness.

For Paul, truth incorporates several key Old Testament themes: creation (God's self-revelation in nature, as seen in Romans 1:20, which parallels Psalm 19:1–4); covenant (the faithfulness to divine promises, mentioned in Romans 3:3–4, and illustrated in Exodus 34:6); judgment (God's wrath against the suppression of truth in Romans 1:18, echoing Isaiah 66:4); and wisdom (aligning with God's moral order, as noted in Romans 2:20 and Proverbs 1:7). Dallas Willard extends this theological vision, arguing that truth is ultimately a matter of reality as God knows it, and that Christian discipleship requires aligning knowledge and speech with divine reality.^{iv} As such, lying or spreading misinformation not only violates social trust but also undermines the principles of discipleship itself. The biblical and theological witness thus converges to show that truth-telling is not a pragmatic tool, but an essential virtue rooted in God's being. It is sustained by covenantal trust, embodied in Christ, and commanded for the building up of the community in love.

Those who perish “because they refused to love the truth” (2 Thessalonians 2:10–12) resemble figures from the Old Testament who rebelled against God, such as Pharaoh, whose heart was hardened (Exodus 7–14), or those who faced exile as a result of unfaithfulness to the covenant (Deuteronomy 28:15–68). Conversely, Paul admonishes believers to “walk in the truth” (Ephesians 5:8-9; cf. 3 John 1:4), a call rooted in the Psalms’ exhortation to “walk in [God’s] truth” (Psalm 86:11) and the prophetic vision of a people marked by integrity (Zechariah 8:16–17). Stanley Hauerwas frames Christian integrity as the formation of truthful character within the life of the church, emphasizing that truth-telling is sustained communally, not merely individually.^v Truth, for Paul, is thus both a theological reality—embodied in Christ as the fulfillment of God’s redemptive plan (John 14:6; Ephesians 4:21)—and an ethical imperative, demanding alignment with divine holiness.

The relationship between divine revelation and ethical living highlights wisdom as a central theme in biblical literature, connecting the instructional messages of the Old Testament with the fulfillment found in the New Testament through Christ. In the Old Testament, wisdom is defined by “the fear of the Lord” (Proverbs 1:7). This reverence informs both intellectual pursuit and moral discernment, guiding believers to align with God’s intended order. This theme is further explored in the New Testament, where wisdom transcends mere abstract knowledge and is personified in Christ. Jesus states that wisdom is “justified by her deeds” (Matthew 11:19), indicating that true wisdom—similar to Paul’s concept of “truth”—is confirmed through righteous actions. Paul deepens this idea by describing Christ as “the wisdom of God” (1 Corinthians 1:24), positioning His crucifixion and resurrection as the ultimate expression of divine wisdom that challenges worldly notions of power and intellect. Likewise, Colossians 2:2-3 affirms that “in Christ are hidden all the treasures of wisdom,” establishing Him as the fulfillment of the Old Testament’s search for understanding.

James further synthesizes these ideas by distinguishing between earthly wisdom, which is driven by “selfish ambition,” and the “wisdom from above,” which is characterized by purity, peace, and mercy (James 3:13–17). Together, these texts reframe the Old Testament’s call to pursue wisdom (Proverbs 2:1–5; Ecclesiastes 7:23–25) as a call to abide in Christ, whose life and teachings embody the integration of truth, justice, and humility. Just as Proverbs links wisdom to ethical living, the New Testament presents wisdom as a transformative force, uniting believers to God’s redemptive purposes and empowering them to “walk in a manner worthy of the Lord” (Colossians 1:10). Thus, biblical wisdom, from Proverbs to Paul, transcends mere intellectualism, inviting believers into a holistic relationship with God that shapes both thought and conduct.

Discernment, closely related to wisdom, is the ability to make judicious decisions based on understanding truth and applying wisdom. The New Testament emphasizes the importance of discernment in various contexts, particularly in discerning spiritual truths and moral choices. For example, Philippians 1:9-10 emphasizes the importance of love to abound in knowledge and discernment, suggesting that genuine discernment is not merely an intellectual exercise but is deeply intertwined with the practice of love. This connection between love and discernment is crucial, as it suggests that the ability to discern rightly is enhanced when rooted in a genuine concern for others and a commitment to ethical living. Alvin Plantinga likewise underscores that Christian belief, including truthfulness, is warranted because it is formed by properly functioning cognitive faculties operating according to God’s design plan.^{vi}

Exegesis of clause “ἀληθεύοντες δὲ ἐν ἀγάπῃ αὐξήσωμεν εἰς αὐτὸν τὰ πάντα, ὃς ἐστὶν ἡ κεφαλὴ, Χριστός”

Building on the integration of truth and wisdom as embodied divine attributes in Paul’s theology, Ephesians 4:15, “speaking the truth in love,” reveals love as the animating principle that unites these concepts, grounding them in the relational character of God rather than abstract

ideals. In Ephesians 4, Paul employs a series of present active participles to characterize the attributes of a walk worthy of Christ.

The participle ἀληθεύοντες (*alētheuontes*), translated as “speaking the truth” or “being truthful,” functions adverbially, modifying the main verb αὐξήσωμεν (*auxēsōmen*, “let us grow” or “may we grow”). Grammatically, this participle expresses manner or means; it indicates *how* the action of the main verb takes place.^{vii} Thus, the clause may be rendered, “*By speaking the truth in love, we may grow up in all things into Him who is the head, Christ.*” Harold W. Hoehner notes that the participle ἀληθεύοντες (*alētheuontes*) in Ephesians 4:15 includes both verbal and behavioral aspects of truthfulness, signifying an ongoing and comprehensive process rather than a single action.^{viii} According to Hoehner, Paul’s choice of the present participle implies that believers are called not only to *speak* truth but also to *embody* it consistently in their conduct and relationships. Thus, “truing in love” denotes an ongoing lifestyle characterized by sincerity, integrity, and congruence between word and deed, all of which contribute to the believer’s growth into Christlikeness.^{ix}

Hoehner’s insight aligns with the broader understanding of sanctification in Paul’s teachings as a process of progressive transformation (see Eph. 4:22–24). In this view, a believer’s speech and behavior are continually shaped by the truth revealed in Christ. By emphasizing both verbal integrity and ethical authenticity, Hoehner underscores that true Christian growth involves understanding truth not just as propositional correctness, but as a relational faithfulness that is lived out in love.

Paul does not use the noun form of ἀληθεύω (*aletheuo*) in Ephesians 4 because he does not want to limit the idea of truth merely to a static description or concept. Instead, by employing the present active participle (ἀληθεύοντες, *aletheuontes*), he emphasizes an ongoing, dynamic practice of truthfulness rather than a mere doctrinal affirmation or an isolated act of honesty. A

noun (such as *ἀλήθεια* – “truth”) would suggest a static quality or a fixed attribute rather than an active, lived-out practice. Paul links truthfulness with love (*ἐν ἀγάπῃ*, *en agapē*) to show that genuine Christian maturity involves both truth and love in constant practice (Eph. 4:15). For Paul, truth (*alētheia*) and wisdom (*sophia*) are not detached virtues but expressions of God’s nature, incarnate in Christ (John 1:14; Colossians 2:3) and enacted through the Spirit-led community.

The participle is in the present active form, indicating continuous or habitual action rather than a single event. Paul’s choice of present tense is intentional; it presents truth-telling not as an isolated act of speech but as a consistent lifestyle of integrity and authenticity within the community of faith. This ongoing practice of “truthing in love” (since the verb *ἀληθεύω* can imply both “to speak truth” and “to live truthfully”) is essential for the spiritual growth that follows in the main verb *αὐξήσωμεν*. Therefore, the participle emphasizes a habitual, Spirit-enabled process rather than a one-time moral action.

Peter T. O’Brien highlights that the participle *ἀληθεύοντες* (*alētheuontes*) in Ephesians 4:15 conveys “the habitual disposition of truth lived out in the sphere of love.”^x This indicates that Paul is not merely urging believers to speak the truth; rather, he is calling them to embody a continuous commitment to truthfulness that influences both their attitudes and actions. O’Brien’s insight emphasizes that, for Paul, truth is not just an abstract concept but a relational virtue—a sustained pattern of living authentically within the faith community.^{xi}

O’Brien’s reading deepens the ethical dimension of the text: “truth” is not only doctrinal precision but also moral integrity and relational fidelity. By interpreting *ἀληθεύοντες* as a *habitual disposition*, O’Brien connects the participle directly to Paul’s vision of the church as a maturing body, growing into the likeness of Christ through ongoing faithfulness to truth *expressed in love*.^{xii} The present tense of the participle emphasizes that this is an ongoing

practice: believers are to make truthfulness a habitual characteristic, expressed in the context of love (ἐν ἀγάπῃ). The prepositional phrase, ἐν ἀγάπῃ (“in love”), functions as the dative of manner, implying the believer's transformation into Christlikeness.^{xiii} Paul asserts that truth must be conveyed with love, never coldness or harshness. This loving manner fosters unity, maturity, and growth into the fullness of Christ's character. This approach ensures that truth does not become harsh or divisive. In this manner, O'Brien presents Christian maturity as the integration of truth and love, where growth in Christ is achieved through the consistent practice of both.

F. F. Bruce expands this understanding by situating the participle within the broader argument of *Ephesians 4:11-16*, where Paul presents the church as a living organism growing toward maturity in Christ, its head.^{xiv} Bruce observes that every member contributes to the community's development “through truth and love,” illustrating that the believer's continual practice of truthful living is both individual and corporate.^{xv} This mutual edification through truth and love ensures that the church grows “in all things into Him who is the head, Christ,” achieving unity and maturity as each part fulfills its function under divine guidance.

Thus, in the synthesis of Hoehner, O'Brien, and Bruce, ἀληθεύοντες ἐν ἀγάπῃ captures the essence of Paul's vision of transformative discipleship: a life characterized by continual truthfulness, relational love, and communal growth that reflects the very character of Christ. The participle ἀληθεύοντες highlights two key aspects: doctrinal fidelity, which means adhering to the truth of the gospel, and relational authenticity, which involves being honest and genuine with one another. By pairing this idea with the phrase ἐν ἀγάπῃ (“in love”), Paul ensures that truth is balanced with charity, preventing any harshness or divisiveness within the community.

Paul’s writing suggests that spiritual maturity and unity in Christ can only be achieved through a continuous interaction of truth and love. The use of the participle in this context sets the ethical tone for the passage: growth into Christ’s likeness (αὐξήσωμεν εἰς αὐτόν) occurs as believers actively express truth within loving relationships. This emphasizes an ongoing transformation of both mind and behavior, echoing Paul’s later encouragement in Ephesians 4:21–24 to “put on the new self... created in the likeness of God in true righteousness and holiness.”

When Paul urges believers to “grow up in every way into him who is the head, into Christ” (Ephesians 4:15), he frames truth-telling as a formative practice that mirrors Christ’s ministry, where truth was inseparable from compassionate action (e.g., John 8:1–11). Love (*agapē*), as the “bond of perfection” (Colossians 3:14), becomes the hermeneutic through which truth is communicated, ensuring it edifies rather than alienates.

This reflects the Old Testament’s vision of covenantal faithfulness (*hesed*), where truth and steadfast love are intertwined (Psalm 85:10; Micah 6:8), and the wisdom tradition’s emphasis on speech that heals (Proverbs 12:18) and rebukes that restore (Proverbs 27:5–6). Paul’s directive in Ephesians 4:15 thus echoes Christ’s embodiment of divine wisdom, which balanced unyielding truth with radical grace (Luke 4:22; John 1:17). Just as James links wisdom to “peaceable, gentle” conduct (James 3:17), Paul insists that love tempers truth, guarding against self-righteousness (Galatians 6:1) and fostering unity within the body of Christ (Ephesians 4:3).

In this framework, truth, wisdom, and love are not competing for virtues. Still, facets of God’s triune nature—the truth as revelation (John 17:17), wisdom as divine order (1 Corinthians 1:24), and love as self-giving action (1 John 4:8). To “speak the truth in love” is therefore to participate in God’s redemptive work, where words and deeds align with the character of Christ, the ultimate *Logos* in whom “grace and truth” converge (John 1:14). It is imperative to

recognize the transformative potential of these principles. Integrating love into truth-telling enriches interpersonal relationships and fosters a culture of integrity and trust within communities. In an era where the concept of truth is often contested, the biblical perspective offers a counter-narrative that emphasizes the importance of relational authenticity and moral courage.

In conclusion, examining biblical teachings on truth, wisdom, and discernment reveals a rich tapestry of insights relevant to contemporary society. The interconnectedness of these themes, particularly the role of love in truth-telling, serves as a guiding principle for ethical living and moral decision-making. As individuals and communities strive to embody these teachings, they are called to cultivate a deeper understanding of truth, seek wisdom in their choices, and exercise discernment in their interactions with others. The biblical narrative challenges believers to uphold these values and invites them into a transformative journey that reflects the character of Christ in a world desperately in need of truth, love, and discernment.

However, the pursuit of truth faces unprecedented challenges in today's rapidly evolving digital landscape. The rise of misinformation, the manipulation of narratives, and the overwhelming influx of digital content complicate the ability to discern what is true and trustworthy. As we transition to exploring contemporary challenges in the digital sphere, it becomes essential to examine how biblical principles of truth and wisdom can be applied to navigate the complexities of modern communication, ensuring that ethical discernment remains at the forefront of our engagement with the digital world.

Paul's concept of ἀληθεύοντες ἐν ἀγάπῃ (truthing in love) goes beyond a simple ethical guideline; it describes the dynamic process of sanctification within the body of Christ. Together, truth and love serve as both the means and the measure of Christian maturity, connecting doctrine, conduct, and community as believers are continually transformed into the

likeness of Christ. Paul exhorts believers to “put away falsehood; let each one of you speak the truth with his neighbor” (Eph. 4:25) and to “speak the truth in love” (Eph. 4:15). The latter verse carries significant weight in Christian ethics. Dietrich Bonhoeffer reflected on the complexity of truth-telling, noting that Christian truth is never abstract but always relational and contextual. Thus, speaking the truth requires discernment, a sense of responsibility, and, above all, a commitment to God’s command to love one’s neighbor.^{xvi}

Christian Integrity and Virtue Ethics

If truth-telling is central to the Christian life, then the question arises: how is this truthfulness sustained within the believer and the church? One influential answer has come through the tradition of virtue ethics, which emphasizes not only rules and consequences but the cultivation of character.^{xvii} Christopher C. Roberts examines the moral framework of Christian virtue by analyzing classical virtue theory, particularly the works of Aristotle and Aquinas, while highlighting its distinct theological foundation.^{xviii} He contends that Christian virtue ethics should be understood as a participatory ethic, focusing not only on moral excellence but also on transformation through grace and conformity to Christ.^{xix} Roberts critiques secular adaptations of virtue ethics for lacking a sufficient explanation of divine agency, asserting that Christian virtue arises from faith, is sustained by love, and is oriented toward communion with God. His participatory reading deepens Paul’s concept of ἀληθεύοντες ἐν ἀγάπῃ (“truthing in love”), suggesting that Christian virtue is both relational and transformative, rooted in the believer’s ongoing incorporation into Christ rather than in the perfection of moral habit alone.^{xx}

Alasdair MacIntyre, in his work, *After Virtue*, argues that modern society has lost a shared understanding of the good, resulting in a fractured moral fabric. He asserts that virtues can only be understood within the context of a living moral tradition.^{xxi} This perspective complements the Christian understanding of virtue as participation in the divine story. In this framework,

truthfulness, like all virtues, is a communal practice shaped by the narrative of Christ. Paul's exhortation in Ephesians 4:15 to "speak the truth in love" reflects the lived expression of a community united in redemption. Echoing Christopher C. Roberts's participatory ethics, this truth-telling is not just about being correct ethically; it is about grace-enabled participation in the life of Christ, where truth and love are essential to the believer's shared vocation. Ultimately, Christian integrity emerges from communal formation within the narrative of grace, where truth, love, and transformation are intertwined.

Building upon the insights of MacIntyre and Roberts, Stanley Hauerwas further develops the discussion by situating the moral and theological formation of virtue within the communal life of the Church. In *A Community of Character*, Hauerwas argues that the church itself serves as the narrative community where virtues are cultivated, and truth is embodied through practice.^{xxii} While MacIntyre maintains that virtues require a coherent moral tradition, and Roberts grounds that tradition in participation in divine grace, Hauerwas emphasizes the ecclesial community as the living context in which this grace manifests through shared worship, teaching, and mutual accountability.

For Hauerwas, integrity is inseparable from ecclesial existence, as the church provides both the story and the practices that uphold truthful speech and moral coherence. In this context, "speaking the truth in love" (Eph. 4:15) is not merely an individual ethical task, but rather the collective vocation of a community shaped by the truth of Christ. Consequently, Christian integrity becomes a communal act of resistance, a counter-witness to cultures fragmented by self-interest, deception, and misinformation.

In harmony with this communal and participatory vision of virtue, N. T. Wright advances the discussion in *Virtue Reborn* by situating Christian ethics within the eschatological horizon of God's new creation. For Wright, virtues are habits of the heart and mind that, through the

Spirit's work, shape believers into people whose lives anticipate the renewed world God intends.^{xxiii} Truthfulness, therefore, is not merely the avoidance of falsehood but the embodiment of the new humanity in Christ, a life in which speech and action reflect the redemptive reality already inaugurated in Him. In continuity with MacIntyre's narrative formation, Roberts's participatory grace, and Hauerwas's ecclesial practice, Wright's teleological perspective adds the eschatological telos: the final joining of truth and love in the consummation of God's kingdom. Thus, Christian integrity is not static moralism but a dynamic participation in God's future, where virtues are cultivated as signs of the world being made new in Christ.

By integrating MacIntyre's communal narrative, Roberts's concept of participatory virtue, Hauerwas's emphasis on ecclesial integrity, and Wright's focus on eschatological telos, we can develop a coherent theological portrait. Christian truthfulness is the practice, shaped by the Spirit, of a community whose words and actions anticipate the ultimate harmony of truth and love in God's renewed creation.

Extending this eschatological vision, Oliver O'Donovan in *Resurrection and Moral Order* locates the foundation of Christian ethics in the resurrection of Jesus Christ, which both reveals and renews the created moral order.^{xxiv} For O'Donovan, the resurrection is not merely a theological event but the decisive moment that reorients moral reasoning by unveiling the true structure of reality—a creation restored under Christ's lordship.^{xxv} Within this framework, integrity is not derived from abstract moral principles but from participation in the resurrected life of Christ, who embodies the definitive triumph over sin and falsehood.

Thus, to "speak the truth" is to bear resurrection witness, to live and speak in alignment with the new moral order inaugurated through Christ's victory. In harmony with Wright's teleological ethics and Hauerwas's communal practice, O'Donovan grounds Christian integrity

in the ontological reality of redemption, showing that truthfulness is ultimately a participation in the renewed creation where all things cohere in Christ. Christian truthfulness is both moral and ontological—a participation in the risen life of Christ that reorders speech, community, and creation around the reality of divine truth.

Continuing this trajectory of formation and participation, James K. A. Smith expands the discussion of virtue and moral formation by emphasizing the liturgical nature of human identity.^{xxvi} In *Desiring the Kingdom*, Smith argues that human beings are not primarily “thinking things” but “desiring creatures” whose loves and longings are continually shaped by the rituals and practices that orient their lives.^{xxvii} Within this framework, truth-telling is not sustained by intellectual conviction alone, but by a habituated desire directed toward God and one’s neighbor.

Smith’s liturgical vision complements O’Donovan’s resurrection grounding and Hauerwas’s ecclesial ethics, revealing that the integrity of Christian truthfulness depends on rightly ordered worship practices that re-form the heart’s affections in alignment with divine truth. In an age marked by misinformation and performative speech, Smith’s insight underscores that resisting deception requires more than cognitive clarity; it demands spiritual disciplines that reorient love, shaping believers into people whose speech flows from worshipful participation in God’s life.^{xxviii}

When considered together, these thinkers illustrate that Christian integrity is not accidental; it is purposefully cultivated through the transformative power of grace within the life of the Church. This integrity develops through the formation of character within the community, the liturgical shaping of desires, and an eschatological orientation towards the kingdom of God. In this understanding, virtue is both a divine gift and a human practice— nurtured by worship, sustained by truth, and directed by love.

In the context of Christian virtue ethics, truthfulness encompasses much more than simply avoiding falsehood; it represents a habit of the redeemed self and a way of being that testifies to the reality of God’s truth revealed in Christ. Therefore, living truthfully means actively participating in the ongoing work of new creation—speaking the truth in love as those being transformed into the image of the One who is Truth itself.

The Age of Misinformation — Challenges to Christian Witness

The twenty-first century has been marked by what some describe as the “information disorder,” a context in which truth is increasingly contested, manipulated, and fragmented.^{xxix} Neil Postman famously warned in *Amusing Ourselves to Death* that the medium of communication shapes not only what we know but also how we think, predicting that entertainment-driven media would erode public discourse.^{xxx} His concern has proven prophetic in the digital age, where social media platforms prioritize engagement and virality over accuracy and truth. In the age of digital communication, the rapid dissemination of information has transformed the landscape of public discourse and societal interaction.

Klaus Schwab aptly captures the status of the digital revolution as follows:

We stand on the brink of a technological revolution that will fundamentally alter the way we live, work, and relate to one another. In its scale, scope, and complexity, the transformation will be unlike anything humankind has experienced before. We do not yet know just how it will unfold, but one thing is clear: the response to it must be integrated and comprehensive, involving all stakeholders of the global polity, from the public and private sectors to academia and civil society. It is characterized by a fusion of technologies that is blurring the lines between the physical, digital, and biological spheres.^{xxxi}

Schwab's assertion about the technological revolution highlights the existence of billions of interconnected devices worldwide, including smartphones, tablets, and computers, all linked through the internet. These advancements have significantly enhanced the dissemination of information, making knowledge more accessible and transforming the way people communicate, learn, and interact with the world.

However, this digital revolution also presents challenges, such as misinformation, data privacy concerns, and the digital divide, which must be carefully managed to ensure that technological progress benefits society equitably. As information continues to spread at an unprecedented rate, responsible usage and ethical considerations will play a crucial role in shaping the future of digital communication and knowledge sharing. Marshall McLuhan’s dictum that “the medium is the message” further illuminates the dynamics of misinformation.^{xxxii} In digital environments, the form of communication — fast, visual, algorithm-driven — shapes not only the content but also the way truth is perceived. This concept of “media ecology” means Christians must grapple not just with false content, but also with cultural habits of perception and attention that make discernment more challenging.

Contemporary scholars have built on these insights. Danah Boyd’s *It’s Complicated* shows how young people inhabit digital networks where authority and trust are negotiated differently than in traditional institutions.^{xxxiii} Zeynep Tufekci’s *Twitter and Tear Gas* highlights the fragility of digital mobilization, where information spreads rapidly but often without depth, accountability, or resilience.^{xxxiv} Once heralded as a tool for democratizing knowledge and fostering global connectivity, the internet now presents significant challenges, particularly with the proliferation of misinformation.^{xxxv} Nicholas Carr, in *The Shallows*, warns that constant digital consumption reshapes neural pathways, diminishing sustained attention and critical thinking — qualities essential for discerning truth.^{xxxvi}

Despite the increasing reliance on these technologies for accessing news and information, the exact impact of these technologies on spreading falsehoods online remains largely unknown.^{xxxvii} Cass Sunstein describes the phenomenon of “echo chambers” and “information cocoons” in *Republic*, where algorithms feed users with information that reinforces prior beliefs, deepening polarization and undermining shared truth.^{xxxviii} While media discussions

often highlight specific instances of false news circulation, large-scale empirical studies do not examine how misinformation spreads and where it originates socially.

Current research on misinformation diffusion is mainly based on small, ad hoc samples that fail to address two critical scientific questions:^{xxxix} How do truth and falsehood spread differently, and what aspects of human judgment account for these differences? Shoshana Zuboff's *The Age of Surveillance Capitalism* exposes how tech companies commodify personal data, manipulating behavior through predictive algorithms.^{xl} This dynamic development not only raises ethical concerns about autonomy but also shows how misinformation is fueled by economic incentives.

The differential spread of truth and falsehood is a complex phenomenon rooted in the cognitive, social, and emotional dimensions of human judgment.^{xli} Psychologists have also explored why misinformation is so persuasive. Gordon Pennycook and David Rand demonstrate that susceptibility to “fake news” often stems less from ideological bias than from a lack of reflective reasoning.^{xlii} Harry Frankfurt, in his provocative essay *On Bullshit*, distinguishes between lying (deliberate falsehood) and “bullshit” (indifference to truth), arguing that the latter may be the greater threat because it corrodes the very category of truth.^{xliii} Jonathan Haidt, in *The Righteous Mind*, explains that moral and political beliefs are often formed by intuitive group loyalties rather than rational analysis, making individuals vulnerable to misinformation that aligns with tribal identities.^{xliv}

According to Pew Research, religious communities are particularly susceptible to misinformation because members often rely on homogeneous networks for news and trust information that resonates with their pre-existing theological or eschatological narratives.^{xlv} Kate Bowler observes that in times of suffering and uncertainty, Christians sometimes adopt simplistic or conspiratorial explanations that provide a false sense of control.^{xlvi} Empirical

research suggests that falsehoods, particularly those with sensational or emotionally charged content, propagate more rapidly and broadly than factual information.^{xlvii} A seminal study by Vosoughi et al. analyzed Twitter data and found that false news stories were 70% more likely to be retweeted than true stories because they evoked stronger emotional reactions, such as fear, disgust, or surprise.^{xlviii} This aligns with the affective amplification hypothesis, which posits that emotionally arousing content, even if inaccurate, captures attention and motivates sharing.^{xlix}

The challenge, then, is not merely external — a world “out there” that is hostile to truth — but internal: Christian communities must resist habits of information consumption that erode their discernment. The age of misinformation demands not only critical media literacy but also theological and spiritual resilience. It is essential to recognize that the rise of misinformation is not merely a technological problem but a profoundly human one, rooted in the complexities of belief, identity, and community.

In a world where information is abundant yet often unreliable, the challenge for Christians is to uphold the truth of their faith while engaging thoughtfully and compassionately with a society grappling with uncertainty and division. While the internet has the potential to connect individuals and foster dialogue, it also harbors the risk of misinformation that can undermine social cohesion and distort the message of faith. As Christians navigate this complex landscape, they must remain vigilant in discerning truth from falsehood, fostering an environment of love and understanding within their communities, and ultimately bearing witness to the Gospel's transformative power in a world increasingly marked by confusion and division.

The Tension of Truth and Love in Practice

Christian ethics emphasizes that truth-telling must always be accompanied by love, yet in practice, these two ideals often seem to conflict. Speaking the truth without love can lead to

cruelty and division, while prioritizing love without truth risks falling into sentimentality or compromise. The core challenge of Christian integrity lies in maintaining a balance between the two. Dietrich Bonhoeffer, in his work *Ethics*, addressed this tension by asserting that truth is never an abstract concept but always “concrete,” a word spoken responsibly within a specific situation.¹ He cautioned against reducing truth to rigid formalism or subjective relativism, emphasizing that truth must always be discerned in relationship to both Christ and the neighbor. To speak truth rightly, therefore, requires humility and a willingness to remain in relationship with those who may resist it. Miroslav Volf, in *Exclusion and Embrace*, explores this tension through the lens of reconciliation.^{li} For Volf, truth is necessary for justice, but love demands that truth be communicated in ways that open the possibility of embrace rather than exclusion.^{lii} Charles Marsh argues in *Way of the Cross* that Christian nonviolence requires truthful speech that neither capitulates to injustice nor harbors hatred.^{liii} He highlights the example of Martin Luther King Jr., whose witness embodied both uncompromising truth about racial injustice and a profound love for enemies. This fusion of truth and love, Marsh contends, is a model for Christians confronting deception and division.

Oliver O'Donovan expands on this theme by connecting truthful speech to the resurrection. For O'Donovan, Christian moral action is rooted in the reality of God's new order, where truth and love are not in conflict but are reconciled in Christ.^{liv} Therefore, the perceived tension between truth and love is ultimately resolved by the hope of the future: Christians bear witness to the future unity of truth and love that has already begun in the risen Christ.

Practical implications abound. Correcting misinformation in congregational life, for instance, requires more than fact-checking. It demands pastoral sensitivity — to speak truth without shaming, to call for integrity without alienating. As Bonhoeffer and Volf remind us, truth-telling

is a relational, not merely informational, act. Christian integrity means that our words must be true but also spoken in a way that serves our neighbor in love.

Discernment and Christian Epistemology

If misinformation undermines truth, then the Christian task is not only to speak truth but to discern it faithfully. Scripture presents discernment as a spiritual gift: Paul prays that believers' love may "abound more and more, with knowledge and all discernment" (Phil. 1:9). James describes wisdom from above as "pure, peaceable, gentle, open to reason" (Jas. 3:17). Discernment, therefore, is not merely cognitive but also spiritual, involving the formation of judgment under the guidance of the Holy Spirit.

Esther Meek refers to this as a "covenant epistemology," in which knowledge is grounded in relational trust rather than detached objectivity.^{lv} For Meek, knowing the truth involves a personal encounter with reality as God's gift, not merely the acquisition of data. This approach resonates with the Christian claim that truth is ultimately personal — found in Christ.

In furtherance of this argument, Alvin Plantinga, in *Warranted Christian Belief*, posits that belief in God can be rational and warranted because it arises from cognitive faculties designed by God to produce true beliefs in suitable environments.^{lvi} His framework shows that discernment is not arbitrary but grounded in God's creation and design. Nicholas Wolterstorff also emphasizes that truth-telling is a fundamental obligation of covenantal life, where speech and trust are inextricably intertwined.^{lvii}

Dallas Willard expands on this idea by asserting that knowledge of Christ represents genuine understanding, rather than just a subjective belief. In his book *Knowing Christ Today*, he insists

that truth is “a matter of reality, not opinion.”^{lviii} He argues that Christian discipleship necessitates aligning one’s thoughts and words with God’s reality.^{lix} Thus, misinformation is not only intellectually flawed but also spiritually harmful, as it leads believers away from the reality as God knows it.

Kevin Vanhoozer situates truth within the drama of doctrine: Christian knowing is a participation in the biblical script, performed in faithfulness to God’s Word.^{lx} For Vanhoozer, discernment requires both exegetical fidelity and practical wisdom, so that doctrine is not abstract but enacted in the church’s life. Quentin Schultze adds that digital living demands “habits of the high-tech heart,” virtues such as humility, patience, and integrity, if Christians are to discern wisely in the flood of online information.^{lxi}

Discernment requires careful attention to the nature of deception. Philosopher Harry Frankfurt warns that “bullshit” is more harmful than outright lies because it demonstrates a complete indifference to the truth. In an era when misinformation spreads not only through intentional falsehoods but also through carelessness and apathy, Christians must cultivate a disciplined love for the truth. This perspective indicates that discernment is both an intellectual and a spiritual endeavor. It is rooted in God’s creation, expressed through covenantal trust, embodied in Christ, and sustained by the Holy Spirit. Therefore, Christian epistemology offers a framework for resisting misinformation by transforming believers into lovers of truth.

Pastoral and Ecclesial Responses

If misinformation threatens Christian integrity, the church must not only resist it intellectually but also respond pastorally. The pastoral task is to form disciples who love truth and practice discernment within the digital world. Heidi Campbell’s research on *digital religion* reveals that digital platforms are not neutral tools, but rather spaces where religious identity and practice are negotiated.^{lxii} She argues that churches must intentionally cultivate media literacy as part

of discipleship, equipping believers to navigate online spaces with integrity. This requires a theology of digital engagement, not merely a pragmatic response.

John Dyer, in *From the Garden to the City*, frames technology as both a gift and a challenge: it extends human capacity but also amplifies sin.^{lxiii} For Dyer, pastors must teach congregants to approach digital media with theological intentionality, discerning how tools shape their hearts as well as their habits. Andy Crouch reinforces this with *The Tech-Wise Family*, emphasizing practical disciplines like limiting screen time, prioritizing relationships, and cultivating wisdom in technology use.^{lxiv} These practices can help Christian households resist misinformation by forming habits of attention and trustworthiness.

Andrew Root, in his discussion on digital ministry, warns that online environments tend to foster shallow relationships and quick judgments.^{lxv} This, he argues, undermines the patience needed for meaningful dialogue. He advocates for churches to create spaces that promote vulnerability and accountability, where members can discuss and question information together without fear of shame.

The Pontifical Council for Social Communications emphasizes that Christian communities should assess digital communication not only by its efficiency.^{lxvi} It asserts the inclusion of the standards of truth, justice, and love. This ecclesiastical voice emphasizes that the internet is a moral space, and churches have a responsibility to educate their members on how to engage with it in a meaningful way.

Practical responses can take several forms:

- **Media literacy programs** within Bible studies or discipleship courses, teaching believers to evaluate sources and recognize manipulation.
- **Pastoral modeling**, where leaders demonstrate humility in admitting error, resisting the temptation to spread unverified claims.

- **Liturgical practices**, which orient congregants toward God’s truth and away from cultural falsehoods.
- **Community accountability**, where members lovingly correct one another when misinformation is shared.

Quentin Schultze notes that virtuous digital living requires “habits of the heart” that only communities can nurture.^{lxvii} Stanley Hauerwas’s vision of the church as a “community of character” underscores that Christian truthfulness is sustained not by isolated individuals but by communal practices of honesty, humility, and fidelity.^{lxviii} In short, the church’s pastoral response to misinformation is not primarily about fact-checking, but about forming communities of integrity. By cultivating spiritual disciplines, theological awareness, and digital wisdom, churches can embody the truth in love, even in a culture of deception.

Toward a Theological Framework for Digital Integrity

The preceding sections have demonstrated that truth-telling is central to Christian discipleship, that integrity necessitates virtue formation, and that misinformation presents unique challenges in the digital age. To bring these insights together, we must articulate a theological framework for digital integrity, one that unites biblical truth, virtue ethics, epistemology, and pastoral practice.

Kevin Vanhoozer describes theology as a drama in which Christians are called to perform their roles faithfully according to the script of Scripture.^{lxix} Truth-telling, in this view, is not simply about avoiding lies but about performing the truth of the gospel in word and deed. When misinformation tempts Christians to play false roles, the church’s task is to rehearse and embody truthful performance before the watching world.

Dallas Willard emphasizes that truth is not optional for discipleship: “Reality is what we must deal with whether we like it or not. Truth is what we must seek if we are to deal with reality

rightly.”^{lxx} This suggests that integrity in the digital age requires aligning speech and practice with God’s reality, even when misinformation offers easier or more attractive narratives.

James K. A. Smith reinforces this with his account of liturgical formation. He argues that communities are shaped not merely by ideas but by practices that form desire.^{lxxi} Thus, Christian resistance to misinformation cannot be reduced to intellectual training alone; it must also involve liturgical practices that direct hearts toward truth and away from deception. Worship, prayer, and communal confession remind believers that their identity is rooted in God’s reality, not in cultural fabrications.

Charles Taylor provides the cultural backdrop, showing how modern secularity fragments authority and multiplies competing narratives.^{lxxii} In such a landscape, truth is contested, and subjective authenticity often takes precedence over correspondence to reality. The church, then, must stand as a community of counter-formation, embodying integrity by bearing witness to an objective truth grounded in Christ.

Nicholas Wolterstorff reminds us that truthfulness is a moral obligation within the context of covenant life.^{lxxiii} The church is not merely an institution of information but a covenant community in which trust sustains relationships. Misinformation, by contrast, undermines covenantal trust and corrodes the bonds that hold communities together.

Putting these insights together, a theological framework for digital integrity can be summarized in four key commitments:

1. Biblical Grounding — Truth reflects God’s character, revealed in Christ, and commanded in Scripture.
2. Virtue Ethics — Integrity is cultivated through the formation of truthful character in the community of faith.
3. Epistemological Humility — Discernment involves covenantal trust, spiritual wisdom, and openness to correction.

4. Pastoral Practice — Churches must intentionally form disciples through teaching, worship, and accountability to resist misinformation.

Such a framework allows Christians to engage the digital age not defensively but missionally. By embodying integrity, the church bears witness to a God who is truth and love, offering the world an alternative to the cynicism and confusion of misinformation.

Conclusion

The Christian call to “speak the truth in love” (Eph. 4:15) is both timeless and urgently relevant in the digital age. From Scripture to Augustine and Aquinas, from the Reformers to contemporary ethicists, the witness has been consistent: truth is not optional, but essential to Christian identity and witness. Falsehood corrodes not only knowledge but also trust, community, and discipleship.

The rise of misinformation has made this calling more complex, as communication technologies fragment authority and reward virality over veracity. Neil Postman foresaw that the dominance of entertainment-driven media would trivialize discourse.^{lxxiv} Shoshana Zuboff demonstrates how surveillance capitalism leverages personal data to influence behavior.^{lxxv} Psychologists such as Gordon Pennycook and David Rand have demonstrated how cognitive laziness, rather than mere bias, fuels susceptibility to misinformation.^{lxxvi} All of these insights confirm that the church faces not only moral but also structural and cultural challenges in upholding truth.

Yet Christian theology offers resources for resilience. Virtue ethicists such as Alasdair MacIntyre, N. T. Wright, and Oliver O’Donovan remind us that integrity is cultivated in communities that embody truthful practices.^{lxxvii} Pastoral theologians such as Heidi Campbell

and John Dyer call for intentional media literacy and digital discipleship, while Stanley Hauerwas and James K. A. Smith emphasize the formative role of ecclesial practices in sustaining truthfulness.^{lxxviii}

Ultimately, Christian integrity in the age of misinformation must hold truth and love together. As Bonhoeffer and Volf remind us, truth is not an abstraction, but a word spoken responsibly, in love, to one's neighbor.^{lxxix} The church's task is therefore both epistemological and pastoral: to discern truth faithfully, and to communicate it in ways that heal rather than divide.

To live truthfully in the digital age is to bear witness to Christ, who is the Truth (John 14:6). It is to resist not only lies but indifference to truth, embodying integrity in speech and practice. It is to model discernment in a world of confusion, and to love in a world of division. By embracing this vocation, Christians can stand as a community of integrity, offering the world not only information but the truth that sets free (John 8:32).

Endnote

ⁱAugustine, *On Lying*, trans. Richard Stothert, in *Nicene and Post-Nicene Fathers*, First Series, vol. 3 (Peabody, MA: Hendrickson, 1994), 459.

ⁱⁱThomas Aquinas, *Summa Theologiae*, II-II, q.110, a.1, trans. Fathers of the English Dominican Province (New York: Benziger, 1947), 1467.

ⁱⁱⁱNicholas Wolterstorff, *Reason within the Bounds of Religion*, 2nd ed. (Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 1984), 81.

^{iv}Dallas Willard, *Knowing Christ Today: Why We Can Trust Spiritual Knowledge* (San Francisco: HarperOne, 2009), 22.

^vStanley Hauerwas, *A Community of Character: Toward a Constructive Christian Social Ethic* (Notre Dame, IN: University of Notre Dame Press, 1981), 9.

^{vi}Alvin Plantinga, *Warranted Christian Belief* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2000), 156.

^{vii}Daniel Wallace, *The Basics of the New Testament Syntax, An Intermediate Greek Grammar*, (Grand Rapids; MI: Zondervan, 2000), 274.

^{viii}Harold W. Hoehner, *Ephesians: An Exegetical Commentary* (Grand Rapids: Baker Academic, 2002), 563.

^{ix}*Ibid.*, 565.

^xPeter T. O'Brien, *The Letter to the Ephesians* (Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 1999), 313.

^{xi}*Ibid.*

^{xii}*Ibid.*

^{xiii}Wallace, *The Basics of the New Testament Syntax*, 167.

^{xiv}F. F. Bruce, *The Epistles to the Colossians, to Philemon, and to the Ephesians* (NICNT; Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 1984), 352.

^{xv}Ibid.

^{xvi}Dietrich Bonhoeffer, *Ethics* (New York: Touchstone, 1995), 363.

^{xvii} Christopher C. Roberts, *Virtue Ethics in the Christian Perspective*. (Eugene, OR: Wipf and Stock Publishers, 2024), 1.

^{xviii}Roberts, *Virtue Ethics in the Christian Perspective*, 25.

^{xix} Ibid. 47

^{xx}Ibid.

^{xxi}Alasdair MacIntyre, *After Virtue: A Study in Moral Theory*, 3rd ed. (Notre Dame, IN: University of Notre Dame Press, 2007), 216.

^{xxii}Ibid.

^{xxiii}Nicholas T. Wright, *Virtue Reborn* (New York: HarperOne, 2010), 36.

^{xxiv}Oliver O'Donovan, *Resurrection and Moral Order: An Outline for Evangelical Ethics*, 2nd ed. (Grand Rapids, MI: Eerdmans, 1994), 12.

^{xxv}Ibid., 20

^{xxvi}James K. A. Smith, *Desiring the Kingdom: Worship, Worldview, and Cultural Formation* (Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Academic, 2009), 25.

^{xxvii}Ibid 46

^{xxviii}Ibid., 60.

^{xxix}“Information Disorder” refers to how information can be misleading, manipulated, or harmful, disrupting honest communication in society. It describes cases where information is misrepresented, either intentionally or unintentionally, leading to confusion, distrust, or harm. Claire Wardle and Hossein Derakhshan popularized for the Council of Europe, where they outlined a framework for understanding and combating information problems. Wardle and Derakhshan categorize Information Disorder into three main types; Misinformation (false but not intended to deceive); Disinformation (deliberately false) e.g., Fake News; Malinformation (true but shared to cause harm) e.g., leaking politician private email; Claire Wardle and Hossein Derakhshan, *Information Disorder: Toward an Interdisciplinary Framework for Research and Policy* (Strasbourg: Council of Europe, 2017), 5.

^{xxx}Neil Postman, *Amusing Ourselves to Death: Public Discourse in the Age of Show Business*, 20th Anniversary ed. (New York: Penguin, 2005), 29.

^{xxxi} Klaus Schwab, Klaus Schwab, “The Fourth Industrial Revolution: What it means, how to respond.”, in: World Economic Forum [Online]. Available: <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2016/01/the-fourth-industrial-revolution-what-it-means-and-how-to-respond/> [accessed 3-31-2025].

^{xxxii}Marshall McLuhan, *Understanding Media: The Extensions of Man* (Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 1994 [orig. 1964]), 7.

^{xxxiii}Danah boyd, *It's Complicated: The Social Lives of Networked Teens* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 2014), 38.

^{xxxiv}Zeynep Tufekci, *Twitter and Tear Gas: The Power and Fragility of Networked Protest* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 2017), 20.

^{xxxv}Shu and Liu observe how the “Pakistani defense minister believed fake news and threatened a nuclear war with Israel.” Kai Shu and Huan Liu, *Detecting Fake News and Social Media* (Switzerland: Springer Nature, 2022), 1.

^{xxxvi}Nicholas Carr, *The Shallows: What the Internet Is Doing to Our Brains* (New York: W. W. Norton, 2010), 77.

^{xxxvii}Gottfried, J., & Shearer, E. “News use across social media platforms”. *Pew Research Center*, (May 26, 2016). <https://www.pewresearch.org/journalism/2016/05/26/news-use-across-social-media-platforms-2016/>

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- ^{xxxix}C. Silverman, “This analysis shows how viral fake election news stories outperformed real news on Facebook,” Buzz Feed News, 16 November 2016; <https://www.buzzfeednews.com/article/craigsilverman/viral-fake-election-news-outperformed-real-news-on-facebook>
- ^{xl}Cass R. Sunstein, *#Republic: Divided Democracy in the Age of Social Media* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2017), 9.
- ^{xli}Shu and Liu, *Detecting Fake News and Social Media*, 1.
- ^{xlii}Gordon Pennycook and David G. Rand, “Lazy, Not Biased: Susceptibility to Partisan Fake News Is Better Explained by Lack of Reasoning than by Motivated Reasoning,” *Cognition* 188 (2019): 41.
- ^{xliii}Harry G. Frankfurt, *On Bullshit* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2005), 33.
- ^{xliv}Jonathan Haidt, *The Righteous Mind: Why Good People Are Divided by Politics and Religion* (New York: Pantheon, 2012), 55.
- ^{xlv}Pew Research Center, “Religion and Digital News Consumption,” 2021, <https://www.pewresearch.org>
- ^{xlvi}Kate Bowler, *Everything Happens for a Reason: And Other Lies I’ve Loved* (New York: Random House, 2018), 115.
- ^{xlvii}Seraphin Altay, Ana-Sophie Hacquin, and Hugo Mercier. “Why Do So Few People Share Fake News? It Hurts Their Reputation.” *Nature Human Behaviour* 6, no. 6 (2022): 764–72.
- ^{xlviii}Soroush Vosoughi, Deb Roy, and Sinan Aral, “The Spread of True and False News Online,” *Science* 359, no. 6380 (2018): 1146–51.
- ^{xlix}Seraphin, Hacquin, Mercier, “Why Do So Few People Share Fake News? It Hurts Their Reputation.” 766.
- ^lBonhoeffer, *Ethics*, 369.
- ^{li}Miroslav Volf, *Exclusion and Embrace: A Theological Exploration of Identity, Otherness, and Reconciliation* (Nashville: Abingdon Press, 1996), 203.
- ^{lii}*Ibid.*
- ^{liii}Charles Marsh, *Way of the Cross: The Challenge of Christian Pacifism* (New York: Oxford University Press, 1992), 77.
- ^{liv}O’Donovan, *Resurrection and Moral Order*, 122.
- ^{lv}Esther L. Meek, *Loving to Know: Covenant Epistemology* (Eugene, OR: Cascade, 2011), 75.
- ^{lvi}Plantinga, *Warranted Christian Belief*, 156.
- ^{lvii}Wolterstorff, *Reason within the Bounds of Religion*, 81.
- ^{lviii}Willard, *Knowing Christ Today*, 22.
- ^{lix}*Ibid.*
- ^{lx}Kevin J. Vanhoozer, *The Drama of Doctrine: A Canonical-Linguistic Approach to Christian Theology* (Louisville: Westminster John Knox, 2005), 43
- ^{lxi}*Ibid.*, 43.
- ^{lxii}Heidi Campbell, ed., *Digital Religion: Understanding Religious Practice in Digital Media* (New York: Routledge, 2013), 14.
- ^{lxiii}John Dyer, *From the Garden to the City: The Redeeming and Corrupting Power of Technology* (Grand Rapids: Kregel, 2011), 42.
- ^{lxiv}Andy Crouch, *The Tech-Wise Family: Everyday Steps for Putting Technology in Its Proper Place* (Grand Rapids: Baker, 2017), 89.
- ^{lxv}Andrew Root, *Faith Formation in a Secular Age: Responding to the Church’s Obsession with Youthfulness* (Grand Rapids: Baker Academic, 2017), 145.
- ^{lxvi}Pontifical Council for Social Communications, *Ethics in Internet* (Vatican City: Libreria Editrice Vaticana, 2002), 10.
- ^{lxvii}Quentin J. Schultze, *Habits of the High-Tech Heart: Living Virtuously in the Information Age* (Grand Rapids: Baker Academic, 2002), 57.

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- lxviii Stanley Hauerwas, *A Community of Character*, 16.
- lxix Kevin J. Vanhoozer, *Remythologizing Theology: Divine Action, Passion, and Authorship* (New York: Cambridge University Press, 2010), 89.
- lxx Willard, *Knowing Christ Today*, 19.
- lxxi Smith, *Desiring the Kingdom*, 134.
- lxxii Taylor, *A Secular Age*, 299.
- lxxiii Wolterstorff, *Reason within the Bounds of Religion*, 81.
- lxxiv Postman, *Amusing Ourselves to Death*, 29.
- lxxv Shoshana Zuboff, *The Age of Surveillance Capitalism* (New York: PublicAffairs, 2019), 125.
- lxxvi Pennycook and Rand, "Lazy, Not Biased," 41.
- lxxvii MacIntyre, *After Virtue*, 216; Wright, *Virtue Reborn*, 36; Oliver O'Donovan, *Resurrection and Moral Order: An Outline for Evangelical Ethics*, 2nd ed. (Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 1994), 122.
- lxxviii Campbell, ed., *Digital Religion*, 14; Dyer, *From the Garden to the City*, 42; Stanley Hauerwas, *A Community of Character*, 11; Smith, *Desiring the Kingdom*, 134.
- lxxix Bonhoeffer, *Ethics*, 369; Volf, *Exclusion and Embrace*, 203.